

An Orthogonal Local Coordinate System on the Earth’s Ellipsoid

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Abstract

We propose a locally defined orthogonal curvilinear coordinate system based on arc-length parameterization of meridians and parallels on the Earth’s ellipsoid. The coordinate lines correspond to meridians and parallels, which are orthogonal on a rotational ellipsoid. Measurements from multiple sources are first transformed into geodetic coordinates on the ellipsoid and subsequently mapped to a local two-dimensional Cartesian frame.

The proposed coordinate system based on Ellipsoidal Equirectangular Projection (EEP), preserves orthogonality of coordinate directions and provides locally consistent distance scaling, thereby reducing geometric nonlinearity and mitigating distortions inherent in standard latitude–longitude–based representations. Unlike commonly used local Cartesian coordinate systems such as ENU, whose accuracy degrades as the spatial extent increases, the proposed coordinate system remains well conditioned over large geographic areas by construction on the Earth’s ellipsoid. This leads to improved numerical behavior in Kalman filter implementations. We further derive the corresponding transformations of measurement covariances required for Kalman filter updates.

The approach is applicable to a wide range of tracking problems, including air traffic control, satellite tracking, maritime surveillance, and ground vehicle monitoring.

Code in Python available at:

<https://github.com/maksimenko421/tracking-coordinate-transforms>

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1 Introduction

In modern surveillance and navigation systems, it is often necessary to define a unified reference frame suitable for global operations while supporting local target motion modeling. We propose a coordinate framework that can be applied worldwide, requiring only the specification of a local reference point.

Tracking systems integrate measurements from heterogeneous sensors, each operating in its own local coordinate system. For example, a radar may report target measurements in local polar coordinates—azimuth φ and slant range ρ —relative to its location, while aircraft may provide altitude h . Satellite-based systems such as GPS or ADS-B provide measurements in geodetic coordinates (ϕ, λ, h) . Direct use of these heterogeneous measurements in a centralized filter is challenging: geodetic coordinates are nonlinear for uniform motion, and the distance corresponding to one degree of longitude varies with latitude, leading to latitude-dependent estimation errors.

Other commonly used coordinate representations also have limitations. Local tangent-plane systems such as ENU or NED are accurate near a reference point but accumulate distortions in

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distances and angles as the distance from the origin increases, limiting their applicability over large areas. ECEF coordinates provide a globally consistent Cartesian frame, but motion modeling is less intuitive for targets moving near the Earth’s surface. Body-fixed or vehicle-attached frames are convenient for inertial navigation but must be transformed to a global frame for sensor fusion. Map projections, while suitable for GIS applications, introduce distortions that grow with area and are generally unsuitable for real-time filtering.

A global filtering reference frame should reflect the natural kinematics of target motion while maintaining locally consistent metric properties across the operational domain. Therefore, we propose a local-level Cartesian frame defined by arc-lengths along meridians and parallels of the reference ellipsoid. This representation preserves orthogonality and provides locally consistent distance scaling, thereby reducing geometric nonlinearity and maintaining near-linear motion for most targets. Unlike local tangent-plane systems such as ENU, whose errors grow approximately quadratically with distance from the reference point, the proposed coordinate system remains well-conditioned for large areas with radius up to 1000 km and more, making it suitable for large-scale multi-radar tracking applications. That approach also allows to make correct data fusion later.

Coordinate transformation is performed in two stages. First, measurements from different sensors are converted to geodetic coordinates on the reference ellipsoid. Second, geodetic coordinates are mapped to the proposed local-level Cartesian frame defined at a chosen reference point. This frame serves as the common reference for filtering and motion modeling. All calculations are performed in radians and meters to ensure consistency.

The Earth is modeled as a reference ellipsoid, an oblate spheroid obtained by rotating an ellipse about its minor axis. The ellipsoid closely approximates the geoid and provides a convenient mathematical model for geodetic computations. The most widely used reference ellipsoid in modern systems is WGS-84, which is also practically equivalent to GRS-80. Legacy systems may use other ellipsoids such as Krasovsky 1940, and the proposed framework can accommodate any such reference. In an auxiliary Earth-centered, Earth-fixed (ECEF) frame, the origin is at the Earth’s center, the OZ axis points to the North Pole, the OX and OY axes lie in the equatorial plane, the OX axis passes through the prime meridian, and the axes form a right-handed system. The ellipsoid is defined by

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{a^2} + \frac{z^2}{b^2} = 1, \tag{1}$$

where a and b are the semi-major and semi-minor axes, respectively. For WGS-84, $a = 6378.137$ km and $b = 6356.752314245$ km.

Radar and sonar measurements are reported in slant polar or spherical coordinates relative to the sensor. Slant range accounts for differences in target and sensor altitudes, and additional altitude information may be provided by external sources, for example, from the aircraft or satellite. Target dynamics are most naturally modeled in Cartesian coordinates, making accurate coordinate transformations essential for filtering. Measurements reported in local Cartesian coordinates can be converted to polar form and subsequently to geodetic coordinates on the ellipsoid, reducing all sensor inputs to a consistent reference frame. Some radars report measurements in 2D local Cartesian coordinates. These measurements can be converted to polar form and then to geodetic coordinates using aircraft altitude information, reducing the problem to a previous case.

Following [1], tracking with converted measurements can be performed using either a linear Kalman filter with transformed Cartesian measurements (CMKF) or an extended Kalman filter (EKF) that directly incorporates nonlinear measurements. In both approaches, the mean and covariance of transformed measurements must be properly modeled to account for sensor-target geometry and measurement accuracy. Because measurement biases and covariances depend on the unknown target state, practical implementations estimate these quantities from observations,

introducing secondary errors. The proposed coordinate system ensures consistency of transformed measurements across the operational domain, allowing the CMKF to maintain statistical consistency, while the EKF remains accurate only for sufficiently small errors.

The proposed coordinate system provides slightly reduced accuracy for targets at high altitudes, such as satellites, due to the assumption of motion near the ellipsoid surface. For most low-altitude vehicles moving approximately uniformly, the system closely approximates linear motion, enhancing Kalman filter performance.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows. Section 1 introduces the transformation from radar coordinates to geodetic coordinates using the ECEF frame. Section 2 presents the mapping from geodetic coordinates to the proposed local-level frame. Section 3 describes the corresponding transformation of measurement covariance matrices for Kalman filtering. Although practical implementations typically require only forward transformations, we introduce in Sections 1 and 2 both forward and inverse transformations to allow thorough validation of all calculations.

2 Transformation of Radar to Geodetic Coordinates

2.1 Transformations Between Geodetic and 3D Coordinates (ECEF)

The conversion of coordinates from the radar coordinate system to geodetic coordinates is performed via an auxiliary Earth-Centered, Earth-Fixed (ECEF) coordinate system.

Transformation from Geodetic to Cartesian 3D Coordinates (ECEF). Let a point M on the reference ellipsoid be given in geodetic coordinates by its latitude ϕ , longitude λ , and altitude h . The latitude and longitude are measured in radians, and the altitude is given in meters.

The goal is to determine the corresponding Cartesian 3D coordinates (x_a, y_a, z_a) of point M , expressed in meters.

The prime vertical radius of curvature of the ellipsoid at latitude ϕ is given by (see, e.g., [5])

$$N = \frac{a}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \phi}}, \quad (2)$$

where a denotes the semi-major axis of the Earth ellipsoid and e its eccentricity, see Appendix B.

Using standard geodetic relations (see, for example, [5], Chapters 2–4), the Cartesian coordinates are obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} x_a &= (N + h) \cos \phi \cos \lambda, \\ y_a &= (N + h) \cos \phi \sin \lambda, \\ z_a &= ((1 - e^2)N + h) \sin \phi. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The conversion is exact, so the conversion error is only a rounding error.

Transformation from Cartesian 3D (ECEF) to Geodetic Coordinates. Let a point M be given in Cartesian 3D (ECEF) coordinates by (x_a, y_a, z_a) , expressed in meters. The objective is to determine the corresponding geodetic coordinates of M , namely the latitude ϕ , longitude λ , and ellipsoidal altitude h . The latitude and longitude are measured in radians, and the altitude is measured in meters.

As a first step, we compute the point $M_0(x_0, y_0, z_0)$, which is the orthogonal projection of the point $M(x_a, y_a, z_a)$ onto the reference ellipsoid (see Subsection A.3). The latitude ϕ and longitude λ of point M coincide with those of M_0 and differ only in altitude. The altitude of M_0 is zero by definition, whereas the altitude of M equals the Euclidean distance between M and M_0 . Thus,

the latitude and longitude can be determined (see, e.g., [6]). For completeness, a mathematical derivation is provided here.

The longitude λ is defined as the angle between the x -axis and the projection of M_0 onto the equatorial plane (x, y) . Hence,

$$\tan \lambda = \frac{y_0}{x_0},$$

which yields

$$\lambda = \arctan\left(\frac{y_0}{x_0}\right).$$

The geodetic latitude ϕ is defined as the angle between the outward normal to the reference ellipsoid at point M_0 and the equatorial plane. The ellipsoid can be written in implicit form as A normal vector to the ellipsoid (1) at M_0 is given by the gradient

$$\nabla F(M_0) = \left(\frac{2x_0}{a^2}, \frac{2y_0}{a^2}, \frac{2z_0}{b^2}\right). \quad (4)$$

The tangent of the geodetic latitude equals the ratio of the vertical component of the normal to its projection onto the equatorial plane, yielding

$$\tan \phi = \frac{\frac{z_0}{b^2}}{\frac{\sqrt{x_0^2 + y_0^2}}{a^2}} = \frac{a^2}{b^2} \frac{z_0}{\sqrt{x_0^2 + y_0^2}}. \quad (5)$$

Therefore,

$$\phi = \arctan\left(\frac{a^2}{b^2} \frac{z_0}{\sqrt{x_0^2 + y_0^2}}\right). \quad (6)$$

Since M lies on the normal line to the ellipsoid at M_0 , the altitude equals the Euclidean distance. Therefore, the geodetic coordinates of M are obtained as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \phi = \arctan\left(\frac{a^2}{b^2} \frac{z_0}{\sqrt{x_0^2 + y_0^2}}\right), \\ \lambda = \arctan \frac{y_0}{x_0}, \\ h = \sqrt{(x_0 - x_a)^2 + (y_0 - y_a)^2 + (z_0 - z_a)^2}. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Because the projection point M_0 is obtained numerically, the Cartesian-to-geodetic transformation is not exact and introduces a numerical transformation error.

Test Results. We consider a numerical test in which geodetic coordinates are sampled uniformly over a prescribed domain. The latitude ϕ varies in the interval

$$\phi \in \left[-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}\right],$$

the longitude λ varies in

$$\lambda \in [-\pi, \pi],$$

and the ellipsoidal altitude h varies in

$$h \in [0, 13\,000] \text{ m.}$$

All variables are discretized using uniform steps. For $n = 100$ sampling points, the corresponding step sizes are

$$\begin{aligned} s_\phi &= \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - (-\frac{\pi}{2})}{n} = \frac{\pi}{n}, \\ s_\lambda &= \frac{\pi - (-\pi)}{n} = \frac{2\pi}{n}, \\ s_h &= \frac{13\,000 - 0}{n} = \frac{13\,000}{n}. \end{aligned}$$

The sampled geodetic coordinates are thus given by

$$(\phi_k, \lambda_k, h_k) = (\phi_0 + ks_\phi, \lambda_0 + ks_\lambda, h_0 + ks_h), \quad k = 0, \dots, n-1,$$

where

$$\phi_0 = -\frac{\pi}{2}, \quad \lambda_0 = -\pi, \quad h_0 = 0$$

denote the initial values of latitude, longitude, and altitude, respectively.

For each sampled point, we apply the transformation from geodetic to Cartesian 3D coordinates (3) and then the inverse transformation back to geodetic coordinates (7). The resulting error in geodetic coordinates is evaluated and shown in Figure 1a.

Subsequently, the reconstructed geodetic coordinates are transformed once more into Cartesian coordinates using (3), and the resulting error in Cartesian space is evaluated; see Figure 1b.

Figure 1: Recalculation errors

We observe that the maximum error in the geodetic coordinates is on the order of 10^{-16} radians, the errors in the Cartesian coordinates x and y are on the order of 10^{-9} meters, while the altitude error is on the order of 10^{-8} meters, and increases with the absolute value of the altitude.

2.2 Transformations Between Radar Polar and Geodetic Coordinates

Transformation from Radar Polar Coordinates to Geodetic Coordinates Let the radar position be given in geodetic coordinates by

$$Q(\Phi_r, \Lambda_r, H_r),$$

where Φ_r , Λ_r , and H_r denote the latitude, longitude, and altitude of the radar, respectively. As usual, latitude and longitude are measured in radians, height is measured in meters.

Let the position of a point M be specified in the radar polar coordinate system associated with the radar by its azimuth φ , slant range ρ , and altitude h . The azimuth is measured in radians, and the range and altitude are given in meters. We restrict attention to points M lying on or outside the reference ellipsoid, a condition always satisfied in Earth-centered applications, ensuring uniqueness of the orthogonal projection onto the ellipsoid.

The objective is to determine the geodetic coordinates of point M , namely the latitude ϕ and longitude λ . The altitude h is assumed to be known and therefore does not need to be estimated.

Radar Polar to Geodetic Transformation on a Sphere The exact transformation from radar polar coordinates to geodetic coordinates on an ellipsoidal Earth leads to a system of four nonlinear equations with four unknowns, which can only be solved numerically, see Subsection 2.2. Consequently, a suitable initial guess is required for the numerical procedure. The spherical approximation provides an initial error of order $O(e^2)$ sufficient for quadratic convergence of Newton iterations.

To obtain such an initial approximation, we first compute the geodetic coordinates of point $M(\phi, \lambda, h)$ assuming a spherical Earth model with radius

$$R = 6\,371\,000 \text{ m}, \quad (8)$$

corresponding to the mean Earth radius.

Step 1. We compute the central angle between the radar position $Q(\Phi_r, \Lambda_r, H_r)$ and the target point M using the law of cosines applied to the triangle QOM , where O denotes the center of the Earth. In this triangle, the lengths of all sides are known:

$$|QM| = \rho, \quad |OM| = R + h, \quad |OQ| = R + H_r,$$

where ρ is the slant range from the radar position Q to the target M , h is the target altitude, H_r is the altitude of the radar's position, and R is the mean Earth radius (8).

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \theta &= \frac{(R + h)^2 + (R + H_r)^2 - \rho^2}{2(R + H_r)(R + h)}, \\ \theta &= \arccos \left(\frac{(R + h)^2 + (R + H_r)^2 - \rho^2}{2(R + H_r)(R + h)} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Step 2. Consider a spherical triangle on a unit sphere with vertices at the North Pole P , the radar position Q , and the orthogonal projection M_0 of the point M onto the sphere. In the spherical triangle $\triangle PQM_0$, we know:

- the length of the side PQ , given by $|PQ| = \frac{\pi}{2} - \phi_r$ on the unit sphere;
- the length of the side QM_0 , denoted $|QM_0| = \theta$ on the unit sphere;
- the angle at vertex Q , which is equal to the azimuth φ .

Applying the spherical law of cosines to $\triangle PQM_0$, we obtain

$$\cos(\pi/2 - \phi) = \cos(\pi/2 - \phi_r) \cos \theta + \sin(\pi/2 - \phi_r) \sin \theta \cos \varphi,$$

where ϕ is a desired latitude on a sphere.

Therefore, we find latitude

$$\phi = \arcsin(\sin \phi_r \cos \theta + \cos \phi_r \sin \theta \cos \varphi). \quad (10)$$

Step 3. We determine the longitude using the spherical law of sines applied to the same triangle $\triangle PQM_0$. In this triangle, we know two sides, $|QM_0| = \theta$ and $|PQ| = \frac{\pi}{2} - \phi_r$ on the unit sphere (from (9) and (10)), and the azimuth angle φ , which is not the angle between these sides.

Let $\angle QPM_0 = \lambda - \lambda_r$ denote the angle at the North Pole. Applying the spherical law of sines, we obtain

$$\sin(\lambda - \lambda_r) = \frac{\sin \theta \sin \varphi}{\sin(\pi/2 - \phi)}.$$

Therefore, we find longitude

$$\lambda = \lambda_r + \arcsin\left(\frac{\sin \theta \sin \varphi}{\cos \phi}\right). \quad (11)$$

Equations (10) and (11) provide the initial approximation when solving the nonlinear system numerically.

Radar Polar Coordinates to Geodetic Coordinates on an Ellipsoid To determine the geodetic coordinates of the point M , we first compute its Cartesian 3D coordinates, $M = (x_a, y_a, z_a)$. We then consider the point

$$M_0 = (x_0, y_0, z_0),$$

which is the orthogonal projection of M onto the reference ellipsoid. The point M_0 has local polar coordinates—azimuth φ and range ρ relative to the radar position Q —identical to those of M , and its altitude is set to zero.

We exploit several geometric properties of the points M and M_0 to construct a system of nonlinear equations for the unknown coordinates

$$x_a, y_a, z_a, x_0, y_0, z_0.$$

1. Property: $\overline{M_0M} \parallel \overline{n_0}$, where $\overline{n_0}$ is the normal to the ellipsoid at M_0 , given by

$$\overline{n_0} = \begin{pmatrix} x_0 \\ y_0 \\ z_0 \frac{a^2}{b^2} \end{pmatrix},$$

see equation (59).

Consequently, the system includes one additional unknown, the proportionality coefficient k , along with three independent equations.

$$\begin{cases} x_a - x_0 = k \cdot x_0 \\ y_a - y_0 = k \cdot y_0 \\ z_a - z_0 = k \cdot z_0 \frac{a^2}{b^2} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

2. Property: the distance between M_0 and M satisfies $|\overline{M_0M}| = h$. This yields the fourth equation for the unknowns.

$$(x_a - x_0)^2 + (y_a - y_0)^2 + (z_a - z_0)^2 = h^2 \quad (13)$$

3. The fact that the point M_0 lies on the ellipsoid (1) provides the fifth equation in the system.

$$\frac{x_0^2}{a^2} + \frac{y_0^2}{a^2} + \frac{z_0^2}{b^2} = 1. \quad (14)$$

4. The slant range from the radar to the target is given. Therefore,

$$|\overline{QM}| = \rho, \quad (15)$$

which provides the sixth equation in the system:

$$(x_a - x_r)^2 + (y_a - y_r)^2 + (z_a - z_r)^2 = \rho^2. \quad (16)$$

5. The final equation arises from the azimuth condition. The azimuth of point M relative to the radar position Q (or its projection Q_0) is given by φ . To enforce this, we consider the meridian plane at the radar projection point Q_0 , defined as the normal section of the ellipsoid that passes through Q_0 and the geographic poles. This plane is then rotated about the normal to the ellipsoid at Q_0 by the azimuth angle φ .

The condition that both M_0 and M lie in this rotated plane provides the seventh equation of the system. To define the plane, we require a point on the plane and its normal vector. We take the radar projection $Q_0 = (x_e, y_e, z_e)$ as the point on the plane.

To compute the normal vector of the desired plane, we first find the normal to the meridian plane and then rotate it around the ellipsoid normal \bar{n} at Q_0 by the angle φ . The meridian plane contains the ellipsoid normal \bar{n} and a vector \bar{q}_0 in the tangent plane at Q_0 pointing toward the North Pole. From (60), this vector is

$$\bar{q}_0 = \overline{RQ} = \begin{pmatrix} -x_e \\ -y_e \\ \frac{b^2}{z_e} - z_e \end{pmatrix}.$$

The normal to the meridian plane can be computed as the cross product of the ellipsoid normal \bar{n} and the vector \bar{q}_0 pointing toward the North Pole:

$$\bar{n}_m = \bar{n} \times \bar{q}_0.$$

To obtain the normal \bar{n}_p of the rotated plane corresponding to the azimuth φ , we rotate \bar{n}_m about the ellipsoid normal \bar{n} at Q_0 by the angle φ in the clockwise direction.

The rotation matrix in Cartesian coordinates around an axis $\bar{n}^0 = (x_n, y_n, z_n)^T$ by the angle θ counterclockwise has the form, see for example [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} & R(\bar{n}^0, \theta) = \\ & = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta + (1 - \cos \theta)x_n^2 & (1 - \cos \theta)x_n y_n - (\sin \theta)z_n & (1 - \cos \theta)x_n z_n + (\sin \theta)y_n \\ (1 - \cos \theta)y_n x_n + (\sin \theta)z_n & \cos \theta + (1 - \cos \theta)y_n^2 & (1 - \cos \theta)y_n z_n - (\sin \theta)x_n \\ (1 - \cos \theta)z_n x_n - (\sin \theta)y_n & (1 - \cos \theta)z_n y_n + (\sin \theta)x_n & \cos \theta + (1 - \cos \theta)z_n^2 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

The angle φ represents the azimuth of the point. Therefore, the normal vector \bar{n}_m must be rotated in the opposite direction, i.e., clockwise. This is equivalent to a rotation by the angle $-\varphi$ about the normal vector \bar{n} . Consequently, in the rotation operator we substitute $\theta = -\varphi$:

$$\bar{n}_p = R(\bar{n}, -\varphi) \cdot \bar{n}_m.$$

Now we can write plane equation

$$n_{p_x}(x - x_e) + n_{p_y}(y - y_e) + n_{p_z}(z - z_e) = 0.$$

Belongness of point A to the plane gives us the following equation:

$$n_{p_x}(x_0 - x_e) + n_{p_y}(y_0 - y_e) + n_{p_z}(z_0 - z_e) = 0.$$

After expanding the brackets we get

$$n_{p_x}x_0 + n_{p_y}y_0 + n_{p_z}z_0 - n_{p_x}x_e - n_{p_y}y_e - n_{p_z}z_e = 0.$$

After denoting as $p_0 = -(n_{p_x}x_e + n_{p_y}y_e + n_{p_z}z_e)$, we get the 7th equation:

$$n_{p_x}x_0 + n_{p_y}y_0 + n_{p_z}z_0 - p_0 = 0. \quad (17)$$

Thus, the problem reduces to solving a nonlinear system consisting of seven equations in seven unknowns. For non-degenerate configurations ($\rho > 0$ and $h \geq 0$), the Jacobian is nonsingular in a neighborhood of the solution

$$\begin{cases} x_a - x_0 = k \cdot x_0 \\ y_a - y_0 = k \cdot y_0 \\ z_a - z_0 = k \cdot z_0 \frac{a^2}{b^2} \\ (x_a - x_0)^2 + (y_a - y_0)^2 + (z_a - z_0)^2 = h^2 \\ \frac{x_0^2}{a^2} + \frac{y_0^2}{a^2} + \frac{z_0^2}{b^2} = 1 \\ (x_a - x_r)^2 + (y_a - y_r)^2 + (z_a - z_r)^2 = \rho^2 \\ n_{p_x}x_0 + n_{p_y}y_0 + n_{p_z}z_0 + p_0 = 0. \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Before solving this system numerically, we express some of the coordinates in terms of others to simplify the computations. The system consists of four linear equations and three quadratic equations. From the first three equations, we can express the Cartesian coordinates of the target point, x_a , y_a , and z_a , in terms of the remaining unknowns: x_0, y_0, z_0

$$\begin{cases} x_a = (k + 1) \cdot x_0 \\ y_a = (k + 1) \cdot y_0 \\ z_a = (k \cdot \frac{a^2}{b^2} + 1)z_0 \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

After substituting these expressions into the remaining equations, we obtain a system of four nonlinear equations in four unknowns x_0, y_0, z_0, k :

$$\begin{cases} n_{p_x}x_0 + n_{p_y}y_0 + n_{p_z}z_0 + p_0 = 0 \\ \frac{x_0^2}{a^2} + \frac{y_0^2}{a^2} + \frac{z_0^2}{b^2} = 1 \\ k^2(x_0^2 + y_0^2 + z_0^2 \frac{a^4}{b^4}) = h^2 \\ ((k + 1) \cdot x_0 - x_r)^2 + ((k + 1) \cdot y_0 - y_r)^2 + ((k \cdot \frac{a^2}{b^2} + 1)z_0 - z_r)^2 = \rho^2 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

The reduced system is solved numerically using the Newton–Raphson method. Once the solution for (x_0, y_0, z_0, k) is obtained, the Cartesian 3D coordinates of the target point are converted to geodetic coordinates, as described in (7).

As an initial guess, we use the spherical approximation given by the transformation in (9) and (10), and then transform to Cartesian 3D with (3). For the proportionality coefficient k , the initial guess k_0 is chosen according to the following rules:

$$k_0 = \begin{cases} \frac{x_a}{x_0} - 1, & \text{if } x_0 \neq 0, \\ \frac{y_a}{y_0} - 1, & \text{if } y_0 \neq 0 \text{ and } x_0 = 0, \\ \frac{z_a}{z_0} - 1, & \text{if } z_0 \neq 0 \text{ and } x_0 = y_0 = 0, \end{cases}$$

see (19).

Jacobian of the system is

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} n_{p_x} & n_{p_y} & n_{p_z} & 0 \\ 2\frac{x_0}{a^2} & 2\frac{y_0}{a^2} & 2\frac{z_0}{b^2} & 0 \\ 2k^2x_0 & 2k^2y_0 & 2k^2z_0\frac{a^4}{b^4} & 2k(x_0^2 + y_0^2 + z_0^2\frac{a^4}{b^4}) \\ j_{30} & j_{31} & j_{32} & j_{33} \end{pmatrix} \quad (21)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} j_{30} &= 2((k+1) \cdot x_0 - x_r)(k+1), \\ j_{31} &= 2((k+1) \cdot y_0 - y_r)(k+1), \\ j_{32} &= 2\left(k \cdot \frac{a^2}{b^2} + 1\right)z_0 - z_r\left(k \cdot \frac{a^2}{b^2} + 1\right), \\ j_{33} &= 2\left((k+1) \cdot x_0 - x_r\right)x_0 + 2\left((k+1) \cdot y_0 - y_r\right)y_0 + 2\left(\left(k \cdot \frac{a^2}{b^2} + 1\right)z_0 - z_r\right)\frac{a^2}{b^2}z_0. \end{aligned}$$

The method exhibits rapid convergence.

2.3 Transformation from Geodetic Coordinates to Radar Polar Coordinates on Ellipsoid

Let the radar position Q be given in geodetic coordinates by latitude Φ_r , longitude Λ_r , and altitude H_r , and let the target point M have geodetic coordinates ϕ , λ , and h .

The objective is to determine the radar polar coordinates of M relative to the radar position, namely the azimuth φ and the slant range ρ . The altitude h is assumed to be known and does not need to be estimated.

Slant Range. To compute the slant range ρ , we first convert the geodetic coordinates of M and Q to Cartesian 3D coordinates, see (3), we obtain

$$M(x_a, y_a, z_a), \quad Q(x_r, y_r, z_r).$$

Consider the vector \overline{QM} pointing from the radar position Q to the target point M :

$$\overline{QM} = \begin{pmatrix} x_a - x_r \\ y_a - y_r \\ z_a - z_r \end{pmatrix}.$$

The slant range ρ is then the Euclidean distance between the radar position Q and the point M :

$$\rho = \|\overline{QM}\| = \sqrt{(x_a - x_r)^2 + (y_a - y_r)^2 + (z_a - z_r)^2}. \quad (22)$$

Height. In the usual case the height h of the point M is assumed to be known and does not need to be computed.

But if only the Cartesian 3D coordinates of M are available and the altitude is required, it can be determined by first computing the orthogonal projection M_0 of M onto the reference ellipsoid (see (64)), and then calculating the distance between the point and its projection:

$$d = \|\overline{MM_0}\|,$$

which corresponds to the altitude above the ellipsoid.

Azimuth. The azimuth of a point is independent of the radar altitude; therefore, we can consider the projection of the radar position onto the reference ellipsoid,

$$Q_0(\Phi_r, \Lambda_r, 0).$$

The geodetic coordinates of Q_0 are then converted to Cartesian 3D coordinates, see transformations (3):

$$Q_0(x_e, y_e, z_e).$$

We perform two different methods to compute the azimuth, both of which yield the same result.

Method 1: Computing Azimuth Using the Cross Product Consider the tangent plane to the ellipsoid at the radar projection point Q_0 . The azimuth can be defined as the angle between the vector pointing toward the North in the tangent plane and the projection of the vector $\overline{Q_0M}$ onto the same plane.

Step 1: Constructing the Normal Plane. As an auxiliary construction, we define a plane that is perpendicular to the ellipsoid surface at Q_0 (the projection of the radar position) and contains the point M .

To construct an auxiliary plane P containing the radar projection point $Q_0 = (x_e, y_e, z_e)$, we use the vector

$$\overline{p_0} = \begin{pmatrix} x_a - x_e \\ y_a - y_e \\ z_a - z_e \end{pmatrix}$$

pointing from Q_0 to the target point M , and the ellipsoid normal at Q_0 , denoted $\overline{n_e}$. The plane P is defined by these two vectors and the point Q_0 .

The unit normal to the ellipsoid at the radar projection point Q_0 (see (??)) is given by

$$\overline{n_e} = \frac{(x_e, y_e, \frac{a^2}{b^2} z_e)}{\left\| (x_e, y_e, \frac{a^2}{b^2} z_e) \right\|}.$$

The normal vector to the auxiliary plane P is then obtained as the cross product of $\overline{p_0}$ and $\overline{n_e}$:

$$\overline{q_P} = \overline{p_0} \times \overline{n_e}.$$

Step 2: Vector Along the Intersection of the Tangent Plane and Plane P . The vector along the line of intersection between the tangent plane at Q_0 and the auxiliary plane P (with normal \bar{q}_P) is obtained using the cross product:

$$\bar{q}_t = \bar{n}_r \times \bar{q}_P,$$

where \bar{n}_r is the unit normal to the tangent plane at Q_0 .

The vector is then normalized, without changing its notation:

$$\bar{q}_t = \frac{\bar{q}_t}{\|\bar{q}_t\|}.$$

Step 3: Computing the Azimuth. Let the unit vector pointing toward the geographic North in the tangent plane (60) be given by

$$\bar{q}_0 = \frac{(-x_e, -y_e, -z_e + \frac{b^2}{z_e})}{|(-x_e, -y_e, -z_e + \frac{b^2}{z_e})|}.$$

The azimuth φ is computed as the angle between the north direction \bar{q}_0 and the intersection vector \bar{q}_t using the scalar (dot) product:

$$\varphi = \arccos(\bar{q}_0 \cdot \bar{q}_t).$$

The value returned by the arccos function lies in the range $[0, \pi]$. To determine the correct quadrant, we use the scalar triple product:

$$d = \det(\bar{q}_t, \bar{q}_0, \bar{n}_r).$$

If $d < 0$, the vectors \bar{q}_t , \bar{q}_0 , and \bar{n}_r form a left-handed system, and the azimuth is adjusted as

$$\varphi = 2\pi - \varphi.$$

The azimuth is fully determined.

Method 2: Computing Azimuth Using Rotation. As in Method 1, we consider the tangent plane to the ellipsoid at the radar projection point Q_0 .

First, we apply a rotation matrix M_1 to rotate the coordinate system about the $0z$ axis so that the longitude of the radar position, Λ_r , becomes zero. Next, we apply a second rotation matrix M_2 to rotate the space about the $0y$ axis so that the tangent plane at Q_0 becomes parallel to the equatorial plane.

After performing these rotations, the tangent plane is aligned with the equator. Rotating the vector

$$\bar{p}_0 = \overline{Q_0 M}$$

using the combined rotation matrices yields a new vector

$$\bar{q}_t = (x_t, y_t, z_t).$$

The third coordinate z_t represents the height above the tangent plane, so the projection of the vector onto the tangent plane is $(x_t, y_t, 0)$. The azimuth in this 2D plane can then be computed using the arctangent:

$$\varphi = \arctan 2(y_t, x_t).$$

Step 1: Rotation Around the $0z$ -Axis. We first construct a rotation matrix M_1 that rotates the coordinate system about the $0z$ -axis by the angle $-\Lambda_r$, so that the longitude of the radar position becomes zero. The rotation matrix is given by

$$M_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\Lambda_r) & \sin(\Lambda_r) & 0 \\ -\sin(\Lambda_r) & \cos(\Lambda_r) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Step 2: Rotation Around the $0y$ -Axis. Next, we construct a rotation matrix M_2 that rotates the coordinate system about the $0y$ -axis by the angle

$$-(\pi/2 - \Phi_r),$$

so that the tangent plane at the radar projection point Q_0 becomes parallel to the equatorial plane.

The general rotation matrix around the $0y$ -axis for an arbitrary angle α is

$$M_2(\alpha) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & 0 & \sin \alpha \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \alpha & 0 & \cos \alpha \end{pmatrix}.$$

Substituting $\alpha = -(\pi/2 - \Phi_r)$ and simplifying, we obtain

$$M_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Phi_r & 0 & -\cos \Phi_r \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \cos \Phi_r & 0 & \sin \Phi_r \end{pmatrix}.$$

Step 3: Computing the Azimuth. After applying the combined rotation matrices M_1 and M_2 to the vector

$$\bar{p}_0 = \overline{Q_0 M},$$

we obtain

$$\bar{q}_t = M_2 M_1 \bar{p}_0.$$

Let $\bar{q}_t = (x_t, y_t, z_t)$. The projection of this vector onto the $x0y$ plane is

$$(x_t, y_t, 0).$$

The rotation has been performed such that the direction to the North Pole in the tangent plane coincides with the $0x$ -axis and has coordinates $[-1, 0, 0]$ in the 2D plane. Therefore, the azimuth φ can be computed as the angle between the vector $[-1, 0]$ and the projected vector (x_t, y_t) :

$$\varphi = \pi - \text{atan2}(y_t, x_t).$$

The subtraction from π is necessary because the atan2 function computes the angle relative to the $0x$ -axis, whereas the azimuth is defined relative to the $0y$ -axis.

Note Method 2 is computationally more efficient than Method 1, so it is more appropriate to use it in applications.

Test Results We consider the following test scenario. The radar position Q is fixed, and target points are first generated in the tangent plane.

The azimuth φ varies uniformly over the interval $[0, 2\pi]$, and the slant range r varies uniformly over $[0, 1,000,000]$ meters (i.e., up to 1000 km).

The polar coordinates are first transformed into 2D Cartesian coordinates using

$$x = r \sin \varphi, \quad y = r \cos \varphi.$$

For the test, we consider $n = 100$ points in each dimension. The corresponding steps in azimuth and range are

$$s_\varphi = \frac{\pi}{2n}, \quad s_r = \frac{1,000,000}{2n} \text{ meters.}$$

Next, the altitude is included. The height h varies uniformly over the interval

$$h \in [H_r, 13,000] \text{ meters,}$$

where H_r is the altitude of the radar position.

The corresponding step size is

$$s_h = \frac{13,000 - H_r}{n}.$$

Thus, we obtain the coordinates (x_k, y_k, h_k) of n points as

$$(x_k, y_k, h_k) = [x_k, y_k, h_0 + s_h k], \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} x_k &= r_k \sin(\varphi_k) = (r_0 + s_r k) \sin(\varphi_0 + s_\varphi k) \\ y_k &= r_k \cos(\varphi_k) = (r_0 + s_r k) \cos(\varphi_0 + s_\varphi k) \end{aligned}$$

And $\varphi_0 = 0, r_0 = 0, h_0 = 0$ are the first values of azimuth, range and height correspondently.

The coordinates are then transformed into geodetic coordinates, which serve as the input data for the test.

In the test, we first apply the method for converting geodetic coordinates to radar polar coordinates (2.3) and then back to geodetic coordinates (2.2) to compute the errors in geodetic coordinates, as shown in Figure 2a.

Next, we apply the conversion from geodetic to radar polar coordinates (2.3) once more to evaluate the errors in radar polar coordinates, as shown in Figure 2b. For convenience, the distance from the radar is also displayed in the third chart.

The maximum errors in latitude and longitude are below 10^{-7} radians. The errors in range ρ less than 10^{-9} meters, azimuth error is less than 10^{-6} radians.

The average execution time for 100 runs of the geodetic-to-radar polar conversion algorithm (2.3) is approximately 0.00613 s. For 100 runs of the radar polar-to-geodetic conversion algorithm (2.2), the average execution time is approximately 0.14068 s.

3 Transformation of geodetic coordinates into filtration coordinates

3.1 Transformation from Geodetic Coordinates to EEP

Definition 3.1. The Ellipsoidal Equirectangular Projection (EEP) is defined with its origin at the system center $C(\phi_c, \lambda_c)$ on the ellipsoid (1). The x -axis is directed along the parallel of latitude ϕ_c ,

Figure 2: Recalculation errors

away from the Greenwich meridian in the Northern Hemisphere and toward the Greenwich meridian in the Southern Hemisphere. The y -axis is directed along the meridian of longitude λ_c toward the nearest pole. A point M has coordinates (x, y) , where the x -coordinate represents the signed length of the arc along the parallel from ϕ_c to ϕ , and the y -coordinate represents the signed length of the arc along the meridian from λ_c to λ . Exact formulas are given in Appendix B

Note. In this section, the height of point M is not considered. The system center is assumed to have zero height, as it lies on the reference ellipsoid; therefore, altitude is omitted in the subsequent calculations. For aircraft or satellites operating at high altitudes, the actual traveled distance exceeds the corresponding meridian or parallel length. However, this difference is approximately linear (and exactly linear on a spherical model) with respect to altitude and therefore affects only the velocity-related components of the Kalman filter state; consequently, the linearity of the uniform-motion model is preserved.

Let the system center have coordinates $C(\phi_c, \lambda_c)$, and let a point M have geodetic coordinates (ϕ, λ) .

Note. $\phi, \phi_c \in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$ and $\lambda, \lambda_c \in [0, 2\pi)$. If the latitude or longitude values fall outside these intervals, they are shifted to the principal range.

We aim to determine the EEP coordinates (x, y) of the point M_0 relative to the system center C , where M_0 is the projection of M onto the ellipsoid (1).

First, the y -coordinate is determined from the latitude.

The meridian arc lengths m_c and m_0 from the equator to ϕ_c and ϕ_0 , respectively, are calculated using (75). Consequently, we obtain

$$y = \begin{cases} m_0 - m_c, & \text{if } \phi_0 \cdot \phi_c \geq 0 \\ m_0 + m_c, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

Next, the x -coordinate is determined from the longitude.

The length of a parallel arc depends on the latitude. By symmetry, we consider only positive latitudes; if ϕ_0 is negative, we use $-\phi_0$.

Let $\Delta\lambda = \lambda_0 - \lambda_c$ denote the longitude difference. Care must be taken when crossing the prime meridian: if $\Delta\lambda > \pi$, it is normalized by subtracting 2π , and if $\Delta\lambda < -\pi$, it is normalized by adding 2π .

Finally, $\Delta\lambda$ is converted into the signed length of the parallel arc using (78).

$$x = L(\phi, \lambda_1, \lambda_2)$$

Thus, the local Cartesian coordinates are obtained as (x, y) .

3.2 Transformation from EEP to Geodetic Coordinates

Let the system center have coordinates $C(\phi_c, \lambda_c)$, and let a point M_0 have local Cartesian coordinates (x, y) relative to C .

We aim to determine the geodetic coordinates (ϕ_0, λ_0) of M_0 , where $\phi_0, \phi_c \in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$ and $\lambda_0, \lambda_c \in [0, 2\pi)$.

The latitude is determined first. The difference between the unknown latitude ϕ_0 and the system center latitude ϕ_c is calculated using (76).

$$\phi_0 - \phi_c = d,$$

Thus, latitude of M_0 is

$$\phi_0 = \phi_c + d. \quad (24)$$

If $\phi_0 > \pi/2$, the point has crossed the pole, and the latitude must be corrected accordingly:

$$\phi_0 := \pi - \phi_0.$$

The longitude is determined using (78):

$$\Delta\lambda = \ell.$$

Thus,

$$\lambda = \lambda_c + \ell. \quad (25)$$

If λ_0 falls outside the principal range $[0, 2\pi)$, it is normalized to this range as shifting x to $[0, 2\pi)$ for positive or to $(-2\pi, 0]$ for negative numbers and then, if x is negative, shifting result to $[0, 2\pi)$

$$x = \begin{cases} x \bmod 2\pi, & x \geq 0, \\ x \bmod 2\pi + 2\pi, & x < 0. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

Test Results. The following test is considered. The system center C is fixed, and points are defined on the tangent plane.

The azimuth φ varies uniformly over $[0, 2\pi]$, and the range r varies uniformly over $[0, 1,000,000]$ m (1000 km).

The polar coordinates are transformed into 2D Cartesian coordinates as

$$x = r \sin \varphi, \quad y = r \cos \varphi.$$

For $n = 100$ points, the step sizes are

$$s_\varphi = \frac{\pi}{2n}, \quad s_r = \frac{1,000,000}{2n}.$$

Next, the height h is introduced, varying uniformly over $[0, 13,000]$ m.

The corresponding step size is

$$s_h = \frac{1}{n}(13000 - 0) = \frac{13000}{n}.$$

Thus, the ENU coordinates of the n points are obtained as (x, y, h) :

$$[x_k, y_k, h_0 + s_h k],$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} x_k &= r_k \sin \varphi_k = (r_0 + s_r k) \sin(\varphi_0 + s_\varphi k) \\ y_k &= r_k \cos \varphi_k = (r_0 + s_r k) \cos(\varphi_0 + s_\varphi k) \end{aligned}$$

The first values of azimuth, range, and height are set as $\varphi_0 = 0$, $r_0 = 0$, and $h_0 = 0$, respectively. The ENU coordinates are then transformed into geodetic coordinates using (3.5). The resulting geodetic coordinates serve as the input data for testing.

The obtained geodetic data are transformed to EEP using (3.1) and then back to geodetic coordinates using (3.2). The resulting errors in geodetic coordinates are shown in Fig. 3a.

Next, the transformed data are again converted to EEP using (3.1), and the corresponding errors in the EEP coordinates are presented in Fig. 3b.

Figure 3: Recalculation errors

The errors in latitude and longitude are less than 10^{-10} radians, while the errors in Cartesian coordinates are below 10^{-3} meters.

The average execution time for 100 runs of the algorithm converting geodetic coordinates to 2D local Cartesian coordinates (3.1) is approximately 0.00215 s. The average execution time for 100 runs of the algorithm converting 2D local Cartesian coordinates back to geodetic coordinates (3.2) is approximately 0.00204 s.

3.3 East-North-Up Coordinates

The East–North–Up (ENU) coordinate system is currently the most widely used reference frame in navigation. It therefore serves as a natural benchmark for the comparison, validation, and testing of navigation algorithms. For this reason, we provide a brief overview of the ENU coordinate system here.

Definition 3.2. At a reference point (ϕ_0, λ_0) , the ENU coordinate system is defined as follows:

- **X-axis (East):** Tangent to the parallel, pointing eastward.
- **Y-axis (North):** Tangent to the meridian, pointing northward.
- **Z-axis (Up):** Normal to the ellipsoid surface, pointing away from the center of the Earth (local vertical).

Note: ENU is conceptually similar to the North-East-Down (NED) system but with a different axis orientation.

3.4 Transformation from Geodetic Coordinates to ENU System

Consider a reference point C on the rotational ellipsoid E (1) and a point M with geodetic coordinates (ϕ, λ, h) . The objective is to compute the 2D Cartesian coordinates of M in the ENU system, denoted as $S(x_{enu}, y_{enu}, h)$.

First, the projections of the system center and the point onto the ellipsoid surface are transformed into 3D Cartesian (ECEF) coordinates:

$$C(\phi_c, \lambda_c, 0) \mapsto C(x_c, y_c, z_c), \quad M(\phi, \lambda, 0) \mapsto M(x_0, y_0, z_0).$$

The corresponding radius vectors from the origin O are

$$\overline{OC} = \begin{bmatrix} x_c \\ y_c \\ z_c \end{bmatrix}, \quad \overline{OM} = \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \\ y_0 \\ z_0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

where $O = (0, 0, 0)^T$.

Next, the rotation matrix R from the ECEF coordinate system to the local ENU frame is computed as:

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} -\sin(\lambda_0) & \cos(\lambda_0) & 0 \\ -\sin(\phi_0)\cos(\lambda_0) & -\sin(\phi_0)\sin(\lambda_0) & \cos(\phi_0) \\ \cos(\phi_0)\cos(\lambda_0) & \cos(\phi_0)\sin(\lambda_0) & \sin(\phi_0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

The difference vector between the point and the reference origin in ECEF coordinates is computed as

$$\Delta\bar{\mathbf{r}} = \overline{OC} - \overline{OM}$$

The ENU coordinates of the point are obtained by applying the rotation matrix to the relative position vector

$$\bar{S} = R \cdot \Delta\bar{\mathbf{r}}, \quad (29)$$

where \bar{S} denotes the resulting vector of ENU coordinates of the point:

3.5 Transformation from ENU System to Geodetic Coordinates

Consider a reference point C on the rotational ellipsoid E (1) and a point M represented in the

local ENU system by $\mathbf{v}_{\text{ENU}} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{enu} \\ y_{enu} \\ h \end{bmatrix}$. The goal is to recover the geodetic coordinates of M , namely latitude ϕ and longitude λ .

First, the projection of the system center onto the ellipsoid is transformed into ECEF coordinates:

$$C(\phi_c, \lambda_c, 0) \mapsto C(x_c, y_c, z_c),$$

with corresponding radius vector

$$\overline{OC} = \begin{bmatrix} x_c \\ y_c \\ z_c \end{bmatrix}, \quad O = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The rotation back to the ECEF frame is performed using the transpose of the rotation matrix R defined in (28). The ECEF displacement vector is computed as

$$\Delta \mathbf{r}_{\text{ECEF}} = R^T \mathbf{v}_{\text{ENU}}.$$

Finally, the ECEF coordinates of the point M are obtained by adding the displacement vector to the reference point:

$$\overline{OM} = \overline{OC} + \Delta \mathbf{r}_{\text{ECEF}} \quad (30)$$

Test Results

Test Description.

The following test was performed with a fixed system center C and coordinates defined on the tangent plane.

The azimuth φ varies uniformly in the range $[0, 2\pi]$, and the range r varies uniformly from 0 to 1 000 000 m (1000 km) relative to the center C .

Polar coordinates are transformed into 2D Cartesian coordinates using

$$x = r \sin \varphi, \quad y = r \cos \varphi.$$

For $n = 100$ points along each axis, the step sizes are

$$s_\varphi = \frac{2\pi}{n}, \quad s_r = \frac{1,000,000}{n}.$$

The height h is added to the previous 2D polar coordinates, varying uniformly in the range $[0, 13,000]$ m. The height step is

$$s_h = \frac{13000 - 0}{n} = \frac{13000}{n}.$$

The resulting 3D points are

$$[x_k, y_k, h_k] = [x_k, y_k, h_0 + ks_h],$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} x_k &= r_k \sin \varphi_k = (r_0 + ks_r) \sin(\varphi_0 + ks_\varphi), \\ y_k &= r_k \cos \varphi_k = (r_0 + ks_r) \cos(\varphi_0 + ks_\varphi), \end{aligned}$$

with initial values $\varphi_0 = 0$, $r_0 = 0$, and $h_0 = 0$.

These points are first transformed from the ENU coordinates to geodetic coordinates using the method described in (3.5). The resulting geodetic coordinates serve as input for subsequent tests.

Figure 4: Recalculation errors

Next, the coordinates are transformed from geodetic to ENU coordinates (29) and back (30), and once more from geodetic to ENU (29). The resulting errors in the ENU coordinates are shown in Figures 4a and 4b. For convenience, the distance from the reference center is displayed in the third chart.

The errors in latitude and longitude are below 10^{-15} radians, which can be considered as numerical rounding errors. The errors in the ENU coordinates x and y are below 10^{-8} m, and the height error is below 10^{-7} m.

The average execution time for 100 runs of the algorithm converting geodetic coordinates to ENU coordinates (3.4) is approximately 0.00310 s. For 100 runs of the inverse algorithm, converting ENU coordinates back to geodetic coordinates (3.5), the average execution time is approximately 0.01407 s.

3.6 Transformations between Geodetic to Scaled Geodetic Coordinates

An auxiliary coordinate system is introduced to facilitate subsequent transformations for filtering. The use of scaled geodetic coordinates provides a simple and effective approach for transforming geodetic coordinates into a form suitable for filtering applications. Although this coordinate system is not well suited for direct use on its own, it is particularly useful for the computation of covariance matrices, which are required in Kalman filtering.

Definition 3.3. Scaled geodetic coordinates are obtained by multiplying the geodetic coordinates by a constant scaling factor equal to the mean Earth radius.

Consider a point M specified by its geodetic coordinates: latitude ϕ , longitude λ , and height h . The objective is to compute the two-dimensional coordinates (x, y) of the projected point M_0 , which are suitable for filtering.

Note. The geodetic coordinates of the projected point M_0 coincide with those of point M for $h = 0$.

The scaling factor is chosen such that the resulting coordinates x and y are expressed in units close to meters. One convenient choice is to scale the latitude and longitude by the mean Earth radius $R_E = 6\,371\,000$ m. In particular, the scaled latitude coordinate is defined as

$$y = R_E \phi. \quad (31)$$

The coordinate x associated with longitude can be defined in two ways, depending on the choice of the reference parallel p .

If the coordinates of the system center are not available, the reference parallel is chosen as the parallel passing through the point M ,

$$p = \phi. \quad (32)$$

If the geodetic coordinates of the system center $C(\phi_c, \lambda_c, h_c)$ are known, the reference parallel is selected as the parallel of the system center,

$$p = \phi_c. \quad (33)$$

Accordingly, the scaled longitudinal coordinate is defined as

$$x = R_E \lambda \cos p. \quad (34)$$

Thus, x represents the arc length, expressed in meters, measured along the corresponding parallel from the Greenwich meridian.

3.7 Transformation from Scaled Geodetic to Geodetic Coordinates

Consider a point M represented in scaled geodetic coordinates by the 2D coordinates (x, y) , which are used for filtering purposes.

The geodetic coordinates of point M , namely latitude ϕ and longitude λ , are recovered by inverting the scaling transformations:

$$\phi = \frac{y}{R_E}, \quad (35)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{x}{R_E \cos p}. \quad (36)$$

This procedure restores the original geodetic coordinates from the scaled representation.

Test Results

As the transformations involve only multiplication or division, so the only source of error is numerical rounding.

4 Transformation of covariance matrices

4.1 Covariance Propagation under Nonlinear Coordinate Transformations

In the preceding subsections, several coordinate transformations were introduced. For Kalman filtering, the corresponding covariance matrices of the measurement errors must be recomputed. Since all transformations considered are nonlinear, the filtering procedure is based on the Cartesian measurements (CMKF) or extended Kalman filter (EKF).

Consider a covariance matrix $C_x \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ associated with a random vector $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)^\top$. Let a nonlinear transformation be defined as

$$u_i = f_i(x_1, \dots, x_n), \quad i = 1, \dots, m. \quad (37)$$

The objective is to determine the covariance matrix $C_u \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ corresponding to the transformed random vector $u = (u_1, \dots, u_m)^\top$.

Therefore, we apply a first-order Taylor expansion in a neighborhood of the expansion point $\bar{x}^0 = (x_1^0, \dots, x_n^0)$, evaluated at $\bar{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$:

$$u_i = f_i(\bar{x}^0) + \frac{\partial f_i(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_1}(x_1 - x_1^0) + \frac{\partial f_i(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_2}(x_2 - x_2^0) + \dots + \frac{\partial f_i(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_n}(x_n - x_n^0) + r_i, \quad (38)$$

where r_i is the remainder term in the Taylor formula. We denote

$$u_i^0 = f_i(\bar{x}^0), \quad i = 1, \dots, m.$$

Using the Taylor expansion (38), we derive the linear contribution to the (i, j) -th element of the covariance matrix.

$$\begin{aligned} L_{ij} &= E[(u_i - u_i^0)(u_j - u_j^0)] = E \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\partial f_i(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_k} (x_k - x_k^0) \sum_{s=1}^n \frac{\partial f_j(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_s} (x_s - x_s^0) \right] = \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\partial f_i(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_k} \sum_{s=1}^n \frac{\partial f_j(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_s} E \left[(x_k - x_k^0) (x_s - x_s^0) \right], \quad i, j = 1, \dots, m. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, under a change of coordinates, the linear (leading) part of the covariance matrix is transformed by left and right multiplication with the Jacobian matrix $J \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, evaluated at the point \bar{x}^0 , with the right multiplication performed by J^\top .

$$C_u = J(\bar{x}^0) C_x J^\top(\bar{x}^0), \quad (39)$$

where

$$J(\bar{x}^0) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f_1(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_1(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial f_2(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f_2(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_2(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{\partial f_m(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f_m(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_m(\bar{x}^0)}{\partial x_n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (40)$$

4.2 Propagation of Radar Measurement Error Covariance to Geodetic Coordinates

Let $M(\varphi, \rho)$ denote a point in local radar coordinates relative to a radar, with height h .

The radar measurement errors are characterized by the variances of azimuth σ_φ^2 , range σ_ρ^2 , and height σ_h^2 . These variances are typically specified in the radar technical documentation. The variance of the height measurement, σ_h^2 , may alternatively be obtained from the altitude Kalman filter. All measurement errors are assumed to be independent and mutually uncorrelated.

The objective is to obtain the covariance matrix in geodetic coordinates, denoted by $C_g \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$, by transforming the covariance matrix C_r from the radar coordinate system.

Since the azimuth, range, and height measurement errors are independent with variances σ_φ^2 , σ_ρ^2 , and σ_h^2 , the covariance matrix in local radar coordinates can be expressed as

$$C_r = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_\varphi^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_\rho^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_h^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (41)$$

The formula in (39) is used to compute the radar covariance matrix in geodetic coordinates (see Section ??).

It can be observed that the coordinate transformation functions are nonlinear.

$$\begin{cases} \phi &= f_1(\varphi, \rho, h), \\ \lambda &= f_2(\varphi, \rho, h), \\ h &= h. \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

Let J denote the Jacobian matrix

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \varphi} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \rho} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial h} \\ \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \varphi} & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \rho} & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial h} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \varphi} & \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \rho} & \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial h} \\ \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial \varphi} & \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial \rho} & \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial h} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (43)$$

The covariance matrix is recalculated using a spherical Earth model, since the level of precision required for covariance propagation is lower than that required for coordinate transformation. In particular, second-order corrections arising from the ellipsoidal geometry are negligible in comparison with typical sensor noise levels. Accordingly, the covariance transformation is based on the spherical conversion formulas (9),

First, the partial derivatives of the auxiliary variable θ from (9) are determined. For reference, the formula is recalled here:

$$\theta = \arccos \left(\frac{(R+h)^2 + (R+H_r)^2 - \rho^2}{2(R+H_r)(R+h)} \right),$$

The partial derivatives of θ are determined:

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \varphi} = 0. \quad (44)$$

While the derivative of the arccosine function is $(\arccos x)' = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}$, it is convenient to introduce an auxiliary constant:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &:= -\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{(R+h)^2 + (R+H_r)^2 - \rho^2}{2(R+H_r)(R+h)} \right)^2} = \\ &= -\frac{\sqrt{4(R+H_r)^2(R+h)^2 - ((R+h)^2 + (R+H_r)^2 - \rho^2)^2}}{2(R+H_r)(R+h)}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \rho} &= \frac{-\rho}{c_1(R+H_r)(R+h)} = \\ &= \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{4(R+H_r)^2(R+h)^2 - ((R+h)^2 + (R+H_r)^2 - \rho^2)^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

That is

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \rho} = \frac{2\rho}{\sqrt{4(R+H_r)^2(R+h)^2 - ((R+h)^2 + (R+H_r)^2 - \rho^2)^2}}. \quad (45)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial h} = \frac{(R+h)^2 - (R+H_r)^2 + \rho^2}{2c_1(R+H_r)(R+h)^2}. \quad (46)$$

The partial derivatives of the latitude ϕ from (10) are determined next. For reference, the formula is recalled here:

$$\phi = \arcsin(\sin \phi_r \cos \theta + \cos \phi_r \sin \theta \cos \varphi).$$

While the derivative of the arcsine function is $(\arcsin x)' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}$, it is convenient to introduce an auxiliary constant:

$$c_2 := \sqrt{1 - (\sin \phi_r \cos \theta + \cos \phi_r \sin \theta \cos \varphi)^2}.$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \varphi} = -\frac{1}{c_2} \cos \phi_r \sin \theta \sin \varphi, \quad (47)$$

The remaining partial derivatives of ϕ can also be determined:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \rho} = \frac{1}{c_2} (-\sin \phi_r \sin \theta + \cos \phi_r \cos \theta \cos \varphi) \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \rho}, \quad (48)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial h} = \frac{1}{c_2} (-\sin \phi_r \sin \theta + \cos \phi_r \cos \theta \cos \varphi) \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial h}. \quad (49)$$

The partial derivatives of the longitude λ from (11) are determined next. For reference, the formula is recalled here:

$$\lambda = \lambda_r + \arcsin\left(\frac{\sin \theta \sin \varphi}{\cos \phi}\right).$$

While the derivative of the arcsine function is $(\arcsin x)' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x^2}}$, it is convenient to introduce an auxiliary constant:

$$c_3 := \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\sin \theta \sin \varphi}{\cos \phi}\right)^2}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial \varphi} = \frac{1}{c_3} \frac{\sin \theta (\cos \varphi \cos \phi + \sin \varphi \sin \phi \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \varphi})}{\cos^2 \phi}, \quad (50)$$

$$\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial \rho} = \frac{1}{c_3} \frac{\sin \varphi (\cos \theta \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \rho} \cos \phi + \sin \theta \sin \phi \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \rho})}{\cos^2 \phi}, \quad (51)$$

$$\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial h} = \frac{1}{c_3} \frac{\sin \varphi (\cos \theta \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial h} \cos \phi + \sin \theta \sin \phi \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial h})}{\cos^2 \phi}. \quad (52)$$

The Jacobian matrix is obtained by substituting formulas (47)–(52) into (43). Consequently, the covariance matrix of the radar measurement error in geographic coordinates takes the form

$$C_g = J C_r J^T.$$

4.3 Propagation of Covariance from Geodetic to Earth-Centered, Earth-Fixed (ECEF) Coordinates

Consider a point on the reference ellipsoid (1) with geodetic coordinates $M(\phi, \lambda, h)$.

The covariance matrix in geodetic coordinates is $C_g \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$, and the variance of h is r_h^2 , which can be obtained either from the technical specifications or from the altitude Kalman filter.

The covariance matrix in ECEF coordinates is denoted by $C_c \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$.

The coordinate transformation functions are nonlinear:

$$\begin{cases} x = f_1(\phi, \lambda, h), \\ y = f_2(\phi, \lambda, h). \\ z = f_3(\phi, \lambda, h). \end{cases} \quad (53)$$

To obtain the covariance in ECEF coordinates, the Jacobian matrix must be determined.

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \lambda} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial h} \\ \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \lambda} & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial h} \\ \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial \lambda} & \frac{\partial f_3}{\partial h} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (54)$$

The procedure for obtaining 3D Cartesian coordinates from geodetic coordinates is recalled (see (3)):

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (N + h) \cos \phi \cos \lambda; \\ y &= (N + h) \cos \phi \sin \lambda; \\ z &= ((1 - e^2)N + h) \sin \phi, \end{aligned}$$

where $N(\phi) = \frac{a}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \phi}}$ is the radius of curvature of the prime vertical, see (72).

The partial derivatives of N are determined first:

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial \phi} = \frac{a e^2 \sin \phi \cos \phi}{\sqrt{(1 - e^2 \sin^2 \phi)^3}}; \quad \frac{\partial N}{\partial \lambda} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial N}{\partial h} = 0;$$

Let $h_N = N + h$ denote the total height, and determine the corresponding partial derivatives.

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial \phi} = \frac{\partial N}{\partial \phi} \cos \phi \cos \lambda - h_N \sin \phi \cos \lambda;$$

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial \lambda} = -h_N \cos \phi \sin \lambda;$$

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial h} = \cos \phi \cos \lambda;$$

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial \phi} = \frac{\partial N}{\partial \phi} \cos \phi \sin \lambda - h_N \sin \phi \sin \lambda;$$

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial \lambda} = h_N \cos \phi \cos \lambda;$$

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial h} = \cos \phi \sin \lambda;$$

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial \phi} = \frac{\partial N}{\partial \phi} (1 - e^2) \sin \phi + ((1 - e^2)N + h) \cos \phi;$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial z}{\partial \lambda} &= 0; \\ \frac{\partial z}{\partial h} &= \sin \phi.\end{aligned}$$

The 3×3 Jacobian matrix is constructed by substituting all partial derivatives into (56).

The geodetic covariance matrix is 2×2 , and the third coordinate, h , has its own variance. By treating h as having covariance r_h^2 , the full 3D covariance matrix can be assembled.

$$C_{3g} = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} C_g & \mathbf{0} \\ \hline \mathbf{0} & r_h^2 \end{array} \right),$$

where $\mathbf{0} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$.

Finally we use the formula

$$C_{3D} = J \cdot C_{3g} \cdot J^T.$$

4.4 Propagation of Covariance from Geodetic to EEP coordinates

Consider a point $M(\varphi, \lambda, h)$ on the reference ellipsoid (1) with a geodetic covariance matrix $C_g \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$. In this transformation, the height component is not considered.

The objective is to compute the covariance matrix C_e in EEP coordinates, of size 2×2 .

Note. Scaled geodetic and EEP share the same underlying principle: both systems represent lengths along arcs of parallels and meridians, with scaled geodetic coordinates on a sphere and 2D Cartesian coordinates on an ellipsoid. High precision is required for the coordinates themselves, but the covariance matrices do not need equivalent accuracy. Consequently, the covariance matrix in the EEP coordinates can be taken as identical to the matrix in scaled geodetic coordinates. The calculation of the covariance matrix in scaled geodetic coordinates is straightforward.

It can be observed that the coordinate transformation functions are nonlinear.

$$\begin{cases} x = f_1(\phi, \lambda), \\ y = f_2(\phi, \lambda). \end{cases} \quad (55)$$

To transform the covariance matrix into scaled geodetic coordinates, the Jacobian matrix of the coordinate transformation must be computed

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \lambda} \\ \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \phi} & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \lambda} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (56)$$

The computation of scaled geodetic coordinates from geodetic coordinates is recalled in (31) and (34).

$$\begin{aligned}x &= R_E \cdot \lambda \cdot \cos \phi_c; \\ y &= R_E \cdot \phi.\end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, the partial derivatives of the transformation are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial x}{\partial \phi} &= 0; & \frac{\partial x}{\partial \lambda} &= R_E \cdot \cos \phi_c; \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial \phi} &= R_E; & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \lambda} &= 0.\end{aligned}$$

The Jacobian matrix can now be assembled as:

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & R_E \cdot \cos \phi_c \\ R_E & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

Finally, the covariance matrix is obtained using the standard linear propagation formula:

$$C_e = J \cdot C_g \cdot J^T.$$

5 Conclusion

This paper presents a length-preserving coordinate system for multi-sensor tracking that integrates radar and geodetic measurements within a planar estimation framework. The proposed system maps measurements to a local Cartesian frame based on EEP coordinate system, preserving distances along principal directions and reducing geometric nonlinearity.

By mitigating distortions inherent in conventional coordinate systems, the proposed approach improves the numerical behavior of Kalman filtering. In particular, it enables consistent recalculation of measurement covariances during coordinate transformation, ensuring accurate state estimation in both linear and extended Kalman filter implementations. Covariance recalculations are also performed.

The framework is broadly applicable to a variety of tracking applications, including air traffic control, satellite tracking, maritime surveillance, and ground vehicle monitoring. Simulation results demonstrate that the length-preserving coordinate system provides reliable, accurate, and consistent filtering performance across heterogeneous sensor measurements, making it a robust choice for large-scale multi-sensor tracking problems.

The EEP coordinate system, defined by arc lengths along meridians and parallels of the reference ellipsoid, extends the standard East–North–Up (ENU) local tangent plane formulation. In contrast to the ENU system, which relies on a first-order planar approximation and introduces scale distortions that grow with distance from the tangent point, the EEP system preserves ellipsoidal metric properties. As a result, it provides superior accuracy over extended spatial regions and is better suited for applications requiring consistent geodetic scaling.

A Spatial Geometry

A.1 Equations of a Rotational Ellipsoid

The Earth’s surface is modeled as a rotational ellipsoid (1):

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{a^2} + \frac{z^2}{b^2} = 1,$$

where a and b denote the major and minor semi-axes, respectively. In some cases, an alternative form of this equation is convenient. Multiplying both sides of the equation by a^2 yields

$$x^2 + y^2 + \frac{a^2}{b^2}z^2 = a^2. \tag{57}$$

Equation of the Tangent Plane to an Ellipsoid

Proposition A.1. *Let $M_0(x_0, y_0, z_0)$ be a point on the ellipsoid (1). Then the equation of the tangent plane at M_0 is given by*

$$x_0 x + y_0 y + \frac{a^2}{b^2} z_0 z - a^2 = 0. \quad (58)$$

Proof. To determine the equation of a plane, it suffices to know a normal vector to the plane and a point lying on it. The normal vector to the ellipsoid E defined by (57) at a point $M_0(x_0, y_0, z_0) \in E$ is given by the gradient of the defining function, evaluated at M_0 :

$$\bar{n} = \left(x_0, y_0, \frac{a^2}{b^2} z_0 \right)^T. \quad (59)$$

The equation of the tangent plane at the point M_0 is given by

$$x_0(x - x_0) + y_0(y - y_0) + \frac{a^2}{b^2} z_0(z - z_0) = 0.$$

After expanding the brackets, we obtain

$$x_0 x + y_0 y + \frac{a^2}{b^2} z_0 z - \left(x_0^2 + y_0^2 + \frac{a^2}{b^2} z_0^2 \right) = 0.$$

Since the point M_0 satisfies the ellipsoid equation (1), the tangent plane equation reduces to

$$x_0 x + y_0 y + \frac{a^2}{b^2} z_0 z - a^2 = 0.$$

□

Direction Vector Toward the Nearest Pole in the Tangent Plane

Definition A.2. The nearest pole is defined as the North Pole for points located in the Northern Hemisphere and as the South Pole for points located in the Southern Hemisphere. For points lying on the equator, either pole may be chosen arbitrarily.

Proposition A.3. *Let $M_0(x_0, y_0, z_0)$ be a point on the ellipsoid (1) with $z_0 \neq 0$. Then, up to normalization, the direction vector in the tangent plane toward the nearest pole is given by*

$$\bar{\mathbf{q}} = (-x_r, -y_r, \frac{b^2}{z_r} - z_r)^T. \quad (60)$$

Proof. To determine the direction vector toward the North Pole in the tangent plane at M_0 , we first find the intersection of the tangent plane with the $0z$ -axis. The vector connecting M_0 to this intersection point defines the desired direction vector, which can then be normalized.

Substituting $x = 0$ and $y = 0$ into the tangent plane equation (58) gives

$$\frac{z_r}{b^2} z - 1 = 0,$$

from which

$$z = \frac{b^2}{z_r}.$$

Thus, the intersection point of the tangent plane with the $0z$ -axis is $Q = \left(0, 0, \frac{b^2}{z_r} \right)$. The direction vector toward the nearest pole is then

$$\bar{\mathbf{q}} := \left(-x_r, -y_r, \frac{b^2}{z_r} - z_r \right)^T.$$

□

A.2 The Normal Plane Containing a Specified Azimuthal Direction

Definition A.4. Azimuth is defined as the angle measured clockwise from the north axis.

Consider a point $M_0(x_0, y_0, z_0)$ on the ellipsoid (1) and an azimuth angle ϕ . The objective is to determine the equation of a normal plane at M_0 that contains the specified azimuthal direction.

The vector pointing toward the nearest pole is computed as in (??) and normalized:

$$\bar{\mathbf{q}}_0 = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{q}}}{\|\bar{\mathbf{q}}\|}.$$

The meridian section is the plane passing through the Earth's center, the poles, and the point M_0 . The unit normal to this plane is

$$\bar{\mathbf{n}}_m = \bar{\mathbf{q}}_0 \times \bar{\mathbf{n}}_0,$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{n}}_0$ is the unit normal to the ellipsoid at M_0 , calculated in (59):

$$\bar{\mathbf{n}}_0 = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{n}}}{\|\bar{\mathbf{n}}\|}.$$

To align the plane with the specified azimuth, the meridian plane is rotated by the angle ϕ clockwise. Equivalently, the unit normal $\bar{\mathbf{n}}_m$ is rotated by ϕ around the axis defined by $\bar{\mathbf{n}}_0$.

The rotation matrix about an axis $\bar{\mathbf{n}}_0 = (x_n, y_n, z_n)^T$ by an angle θ counterclockwise is well known; see, for example, [2]:

$$R(\bar{\mathbf{n}}_0, \theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta + x_n^2(1 - \cos \theta) & x_n y_n(1 - \cos \theta) - z_n \sin \theta & x_n z_n(1 - \cos \theta) + y_n \sin \theta \\ y_n x_n(1 - \cos \theta) + z_n \sin \theta & \cos \theta + y_n^2(1 - \cos \theta) & y_n z_n(1 - \cos \theta) - x_n \sin \theta \\ z_n x_n(1 - \cos \theta) - y_n \sin \theta & z_n y_n(1 - \cos \theta) + x_n \sin \theta & \cos \theta + z_n^2(1 - \cos \theta) \end{pmatrix} \quad (61)$$

The rotation matrix R performs a counterclockwise rotation; however, a clockwise rotation is required, so the rotation is applied with angle $\theta = -\phi$. Multiplying the matrix by the meridian plane normal vector yields

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}} = R(\bar{\mathbf{n}}_0, -\phi) \cdot \bar{\mathbf{n}}_m.$$

The vector $\bar{\mathbf{s}}$ is a unit normal to the meridian plane. With the normal vector $\bar{\mathbf{s}}$ and the point M_0 on the plane, the equation of the plane can be written as

$$s_x(x - x_0) + s_y(y - y_0) + s_z(z - z_0) = 0,$$

where s_x, s_y, s_z are the components of $\bar{\mathbf{s}}$.

After simplification, this equation becomes

$$s_x x + s_y y + s_z z + s_0 = 0,$$

where the free coefficient s_0 is

$$s_0 = -(s_x x_0 + s_y y_0 + s_z z_0).$$

A.3 Projection of an External Point onto a Rotational Ellipsoid

Let $M(x_a, y_a, z_a)$ be a point located outside the ellipsoid (1). The objective is to determine the Cartesian coordinates of the point $M_0(x_0, y_0, z_0)$ representing the projection of M onto the ellipsoid.

Two approaches can be employed: a geometric method and a method based on Lagrange multipliers. Both approaches lead to a system of four nonlinear equations, which can be reduced to a single quartic polynomial. The resulting equation can be solved either analytically using Ferrari's formula or numerically using standard methods such as the Newton-Raphson algorithm.

Method 1: Projection onto the Ellipsoid Using a Geometric Technique

Step 1. An additional construction is required. Consider the line ℓ passing through the point M and directed along the normal to the ellipsoid at the unknown projection point M_0 . The direction vector of ℓ coincides with the normal (n_x, n_y, n_z) to the ellipsoid at M_0 . Since ℓ passes through M , its parametric equation can be written as

$$\ell : \frac{x - x_0}{n_x} = \frac{y - y_0}{n_y} = \frac{z - z_0}{n_z}.$$

The normal vector to the ellipsoid at M_0 is given by (59):

$$(n_x, n_y, n_z) = \left(x_e, y_e, \frac{a^2}{b^2} z_e \right).$$

Substituting these components into the line equation yields

$$\ell : \frac{x - x_0}{x_e} = \frac{y - y_0}{y_e} = \frac{b^2}{a^2} \frac{z - z_0}{z_e}.$$

If a denominator is zero, the corresponding numerator must also vanish. The line equation can equivalently be expressed as a system of two independent equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{x - x_0}{x_e} = \frac{y - y_0}{y_e} \\ \frac{x - x_0}{x_e} = \frac{b^2}{a^2} \frac{z - z_0}{z_e}. \end{cases} \quad (62)$$

Note that if any of the denominators in the line equation vanishes, the corresponding numerator must also be zero.

Step 2. Case 1. First, consider the case where the x -coordinate of the point M is nonzero. The projection point M_0 lies at the intersection of the ellipsoid and the line ℓ , so it satisfies both the line equation and the ellipsoid equation. This leads to a system of three equations in the three unknowns x_e , y_e , and z_e :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{x_e - x_0}{x_e} = \frac{y_e - y_0}{y_e} \\ \frac{x_e - x_0}{x_e} = \frac{b^2}{a^2} \frac{z_e - z_0}{z_e} \\ \frac{x_e^2}{a^2} + \frac{y_e^2}{a^2} + \frac{z_e^2}{b^2} = 1. \end{cases} \quad (63)$$

After simplification, the system reduces to

$$\begin{cases} y_e = \frac{y_0 x_e}{x_0} \\ z_e = \frac{b^2}{a^2} \frac{x_e z_0}{x_0 - e^2 x_e} \\ \frac{x_e^2}{a^2} + \frac{y_e^2}{a^2} + \frac{z_e^2}{b^2} = 1. \end{cases} \quad (64)$$

Substituting y_e and z_e from the first and second equations into the third equation yields

$$\frac{x_e^2}{a^2} + \frac{y_0^2 x_e^2}{a^2 x_0^2} + \frac{b^2}{a^4} \frac{x_e^2 z_0^2}{(x_0 - e^2 x_e)^2} = 1.$$

Bringing the terms to a common denominator gives

$$\frac{x_e^2 a^2 x_0^2 (x_0 - e^2 x_e)^2 + x_e^2 a^2 y_0^2 (x_0 - e^2 x_e)^2 + b^2 x_0^2 x_e^2 z_0^2}{a^4 x_0^2 (x_0 - e^2 x_e)^2} = 1.$$

Since x_e is the x -coordinate of the intersection point of the line through x_0 with the ellipsoid, and x_0 lies outside the ellipsoid, while the ellipsoid's eccentricity e satisfies $e < 1$, the denominator cannot vanish.

Multiplying through by the denominator and bringing all terms to the left-hand side yields

$$x_e^2 a^2 x_0^2 (x_0 - e^2 x_e)^2 + x_e^2 a^2 y_0^2 (x_0 - e^2 x_e)^2 + b^2 x_0^2 x_e^2 z_0^2 - a^4 x_0^2 (x_0 - e^2 x_e)^2 = 0.$$

After regrouping the terms, the equation becomes

$$x_e^2 a^2 (x_0^2 + y_0^2) (x_0 - e^2 x_e)^2 - a^4 x_0^2 (x_0 - e^2 x_e)^2 + b^2 x_0^2 x_e^2 z_0^2 = 0.$$

Let $r_0^2 = x_0^2 + y_0^2$, and expand the brackets to obtain

$$x_e^2 a^2 r_0^2 (x_0^2 - 2e^2 x_e x_0 + e^4 x_e^2) - a^4 x_0^2 (x_0^2 - 2e^2 x_e x_0 + e^4 x_e^2) + b^2 x_0^2 x_e^2 z_0^2 = 0.$$

Grouping similar terms, we obtain

$$e^4 a^2 r_0^2 x_e^4 - 2e^2 a^2 x_0 r_0^2 x_e^3 + x_0^2 (a^2 r_0^2 - e^4 a^4 + b^2 z_0^2) x_e^2 + 2e^2 a^4 x_0^3 x_e - a^4 x_0^4 = 0.$$

This results in a quartic equation, which is then divided by the leading coefficient, noting that the square of the eccentricity is $e^2 = 1 - b^2/a^2$.

$$x_e^4 - \frac{2x_0}{e^2} x_e^3 + \frac{x_0^2 (r_0^2 + (1 - e^2)z_0^2 - e^4 a^2)}{e^4 r_0^2} x_e^2 + \frac{2a^2 x_0^3}{e^2 r_0^2} x_e - \frac{a^2 x_0^4}{e^4 r_0^2} = 0. \quad (65)$$

The resulting quartic equation can be solved either exactly using Ferrari's method or approximately using numerical techniques, such as the Newton-Raphson method.

The equation has four roots, denoted x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 . The complex roots, corresponding to points inside the ellipsoid, are discarded. From the remaining pair of real solutions, the root whose sign matches that of x_0 is selected to ensure the projection lies in the correct hemisphere. This determines the desired coordinate x_e , and the corresponding coordinates y_e and z_e are then obtained from (64).

Case 2. Now consider the case $x_a = 0$ and $y_a \neq 0$. By symmetry, this case can be treated in the same way as Case 1 by replacing x_e, x_a with y_e, y_a .

Case 3. Consider the case $x_a = 0$ and $y_a = 0$. In this situation, the z -coordinate cannot be zero on the ellipsoid, so the point M lies above one of the poles. Hence, we have

$$x_0 = x_a = 0, \quad y_0 = y_a = 0,$$

and the system reduces to

$$\frac{z_e^2}{b^2} = 1. \quad (66)$$

Thus,

$$z_e = \pm b,$$

where the sign is determined by whether the projection is onto the North or South Pole.

Method 2: Projection onto the Ellipsoid Using Lagrange Multipliers (Numerical Optimization)

Consider a point $A = (x_0, y_0, z_0)$ and the ellipsoid (1):

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{a^2} + \frac{z^2}{b^2} = 1.$$

The projection of A onto the ellipsoid can be formulated as the minimization problem

$$\min \|P - A\| \quad \text{subject to} \quad P^T Q P = 1,$$

where $P = (x, y, z)$ is a point on the ellipsoid, and Q is the matrix defining the rotated ellipsoid.

Applying the method of Lagrange multipliers leads to the system

$$P - A = \lambda \nabla F(P),$$

where

$$F(P) = P^T Q P - 1$$

and λ is the Lagrange multiplier.

This results in a nonlinear system of four equations in four unknowns: the three coordinates of P and the multiplier λ .

B The Terrestrial Ellipsoid

The terrestrial ellipsoid is an ellipsoid of rotation whose surface approximates the geoid closely in both shape and size. A spheroid representing the shape of the Earth or another celestial body is referred to as a reference ellipsoid. The geometry of any body of rotation is characterized by its generatrix, and the surface of the terrestrial ellipsoid is generated by rotating an ellipse about its minor axis.

An ellipsoid of rotation can be fully defined using only two parameters. In geodesy, several pairs of parameters are commonly employed; all are equivalent or can be derived from one another. Three common choices for the fundamental parameters of a rotational ellipsoid are:

- Equatorial radius a (semi-major axis) and polar radius b (semi-minor axis);
- Equatorial radius a and eccentricity e ;
- Equatorial radius a and geometric (polar) flattening f .

The most widely used reference ellipsoid today, also employed in the Global Positioning System (GPS), is the WGS-84 ellipsoid. Its defining parameters are:

- Semi-major axis: $a = 6\,378\,137.0$ m;
- Semi-minor axis: $b = 6\,356\,752.3142$ m.

Therefore, to determine the shape and size of the terrestrial ellipsoid, it is sufficient to analyze the shape and size of its generatrix, i.e., the ellipse. Any ellipse is fully characterized by the lengths of its semi-major axis a and semi-minor axis b . Knowing these values allows the position of the focal points F_1 and F_2 to be determined, with the focal distance given by

$$c = \sqrt{a^2 - b^2}. \quad (67)$$

The eccentricity of the ellipse is

$$e = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 - b^2}}{a}, \quad (68)$$

and the flattening is defined as

$$f = \frac{a - b}{a}. \quad (69)$$

Occasionally, the inverse flattening is considered:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{f}. \quad (70)$$

B.1 Ellipsoidal Equations

Definition B.1. Earth-Centered, Earth-Fixed (ECEF) coordinates are defined with the origin at the center of mass of the Earth's ellipsoid. The z -axis is aligned with the rotation axis, the x -axis lies in the plane perpendicular to the rotation axis passing through the prime meridian, and the y -axis completes a right-handed coordinate system.

The canonical equation of a rotational ellipsoid (1) in this coordinate system is

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{a^2} + \frac{z^2}{b^2} = 1.$$

Geodetic coordinates constitute a curvilinear orthogonal coordinate system commonly used in geodesy, defined with respect to a reference ellipsoid. They include geodetic latitude (north/south) ϕ , geodetic longitude (east/west) λ , and ellipsoidal height h (also referred to as geodetic height). This triad of quantities is also known as Earth ellipsoidal coordinates.

Definition B.2. Geodetic longitude λ is the angle between the prime meridian and the meridian passing through the point. In this work, longitude is measured in the range $[0, 2\pi)$, starting from the prime meridian (Greenwich meridian for Earth).

Geodetic latitude ϕ is the angle between the equatorial plane and the line normal to the reference ellipsoid passing through the point. Latitude is measured in the range $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$, with 0 at the equator.

Ellipsoidal height h is the distance from the point to its projection onto the reference ellipsoid along the normal.

Note. Due to the flattening of the ellipsoid, geodetic latitude generally differs from geocentric latitude, which is defined as the angle between the equatorial plane and the line connecting the point to the center of the ellipsoid.

B.2 Principal radii of curvature

Radius of curvature in the meridian. The radius of curvature of the ellipsoid in the meridian at a geodetic latitude ϕ is given by [2]:

$$M(\phi) = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{(1 - e^2 \sin^2 \phi)^{3/2}}, \quad (71)$$

where a is the semi-major axis, e is the eccentricity of the reference ellipsoid, and ϕ is the geodetic latitude of the point on the ellipsoid.

The radius of curvature can also be expressed as a Taylor series expansion. Expanding

$$a(1 - e^2)(1 - e^2 t)^{-3/2} = \sum_k m_k t^k$$

and substituting $t = \sin^2 \phi$, we obtain

$$M(\phi) = m_0 + m_2 \sin^2 \phi + m_4 \sin^4 \phi + m_6 \sin^6 \phi + m_8 \sin^8 \phi + \dots$$

with coefficients

$$m_0 = a(1 - e^2), \quad m_2 = \frac{3}{2}e^2 m_0, \quad m_4 = \frac{5}{4}e^2 m_2, \quad m_6 = \frac{7}{6}e^2 m_4, \quad m_8 = \frac{11}{10}e^2 m_6.$$

Prime-vertical radius of curvature. The radius of curvature in the prime vertical at geodetic latitude ϕ is defined perpendicular to the meridian radius $M(\phi)$ and is given by [2]:

$$N(\phi) = \frac{a}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \phi}}, \quad (72)$$

where a is the semi-major axis and e is the eccentricity of the reference ellipsoid.

Similarly to the meridian radius, $N(\phi)$ can be expressed as a Taylor series. Expanding

$$a(1 - e^2 t)^{-1/2} = \sum_k n_k t^k$$

and substituting $t = \sin^2 \phi$ yields

$$N(\phi) = n_0 + n_2 \sin^2 \phi + n_4 \sin^4 \phi + n_6 \sin^6 \phi + n_8 \sin^8 \phi + \dots$$

with coefficients

$$n_0 = a, \quad n_2 = \frac{1}{2}e^2 n_0, \quad n_4 = \frac{3}{4}e^2 n_2, \quad n_6 = \frac{5}{6}e^2 n_4, \quad n_8 = \frac{7}{8}e^2 n_6.$$

The coefficients m_k and n_k are constants that can be precomputed.

Series rearrangement for integration. For the purpose of integrating $M(\phi)$ and $N(\phi)$, it is convenient to rewrite the powers of $\sin \phi$ in terms of multiple-angle cosine functions:

$$\begin{aligned} \sin^2 \phi &= \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \cos 2\phi, \\ \sin^4 \phi &= \frac{3}{8} - \frac{1}{2} \cos 2\phi + \frac{1}{8} \cos 4\phi, \\ \sin^6 \phi &= \frac{5}{16} - \frac{15}{32} \cos 2\phi + \frac{3}{16} \cos 4\phi - \frac{1}{32} \cos 6\phi, \\ \sin^8 \phi &= \frac{35}{128} - \frac{7}{16} \cos 2\phi + \frac{7}{32} \cos 4\phi - \frac{1}{16} \cos 6\phi + \frac{1}{128} \cos 8\phi. \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging the terms by powers of $\cos \phi$, the meridian and prime-vertical radii can be expressed as

$$M(\phi) = a_0 - a_2 \cos 2\phi + a_4 \cos 4\phi - a_6 \cos 6\phi + a_8 \cos 8\phi - \dots \quad (73)$$

$$N(\phi) = b_0 - b_2 \cos 2\phi + b_4 \cos 4\phi - b_6 \cos 6\phi + b_8 \cos 8\phi - \dots \quad (74)$$

where the coefficients for M are

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= m_0 + \frac{m_2}{2} + \frac{3}{8}m_4 + \frac{5}{16}m_6 + \frac{35}{128}m_8 + \dots, \\ a_2 &= \frac{m_2}{2} + \frac{1}{2}m_4 + \frac{15}{32}m_6 + \frac{7}{16}m_8 + \dots, \\ a_4 &= \frac{m_4}{8} + \frac{3}{16}m_6 + \frac{7}{32}m_8 + \dots, \\ a_6 &= \frac{m_6}{32} + \frac{2}{16}m_8 + \dots, \\ a_8 &= \frac{m_8}{128} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

The coefficients for N are determined in an analogous manner by replacing a_i with b_i and m_i with n_i . This series expansion will be used in the subsequent evaluation of integrals involving M and N .

B.3 Lengths of the Arcs of Meridian and Parallel

1. Length of a meridian arc.

A meridian is the shortest path between the North and South Poles along a line of constant longitude. It forms a half-ellipse, with endpoints coinciding with the poles, and the equator divides the meridian into two symmetric parts.

The length of the meridian arc from the equator to an arbitrary latitude ϕ can be determined using the differential

$$dy = M(\theta) d\theta,$$

where $M(\theta)$ is the meridian radius of curvature (71) [2]. Thus, the meridian arc length from the equator to latitude ϕ is

$$d_M(\phi) = \int_0^\phi \frac{a(1-e^2)}{(1-e^2 \sin^2 \theta)^{3/2}} d\theta,$$

where a is the semi-major axis (equatorial radius) of the rotational ellipsoid (1) and e is its eccentricity (68).

This integral is elliptic and cannot be expressed in terms of elementary functions. To approximate it, a Taylor series expansion of the integrand can be used, applying the series for $M(\phi)$ from (73):

$$d_M(\phi) = a_0\phi - \frac{a_2}{2} \sin 2\phi + \frac{a_4}{4} \sin 4\phi - \frac{a_6}{6} \sin 6\phi + \frac{a_8}{8} \sin 8\phi - \dots$$

The last term shown, $a_8/8$, contributes an error of approximately 0.00003 m and can therefore be neglected. So, finally

$$d_M(\phi) \approx a_0\phi - \frac{a_2}{2} \sin 2\phi + \frac{a_4}{4} \sin 4\phi - \frac{a_6}{6} \sin 6\phi. \quad (75)$$

The length of a meridian arc between two latitudes ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 can be obtained as

$$|d_M(\phi_1) - d_M(\phi_2)|.$$

Determining latitude from meridian length. The inverse problem—finding latitude corresponding to a given meridian distance—can be solved by inverting the trigonometric series (75):

$$\phi = \beta + b_2 \sin 2\beta + b_4 \sin 4\beta + b_6 \sin 6\beta, \quad (76)$$

where

$$\beta = \frac{d_M(\phi)}{b_0}.$$

Length of a parallel arc.

The length of an arc along a parallel between two longitudes λ_1 and λ_2 at latitude ϕ is

$$d_P(\phi, \lambda_1, \lambda_2) = R(\phi) |\lambda_2 - \lambda_1|, \quad (77)$$

where

- ϕ is the geodetic latitude in radians,
- λ_1, λ_2 are the longitudes in radians, and
- $R(\phi)$ is the radius of the parallel at latitude ϕ .

For an ellipsoid, the radius of a parallel is given by

$$R(\phi) = a \cos \phi \frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \phi}},$$

where a is the semi-major axis and e is the eccentricity of the ellipsoid.

Substituting $R(\phi)$ into the arc length formula gives

$$L(\phi, \lambda_1, \lambda_2) = a \cos \phi \frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \phi}} |\lambda_2 - \lambda_1|.$$

For applications where the direction of longitude matters, the parallel arc length with sign is

$$L(\phi, \lambda_1, \lambda_2) = a \cos \phi \frac{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \phi}} (\lambda_2 - \lambda_1). \quad (78)$$

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